

Conference Abstract

Looking beyond the water's edge; ex-situ activities for the European mudminnow, *Umbra krameri*

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Abstract

For many years, Schönbrunn Zoo in Vienna has been maintaining ex-situ-populations of highly endangered freshwater fish species.

Most of these species are micro endemic, inhabiting extremely small areas. These species often consist of a single population whose individuals are usually in permanent contact with each other.

In the case of species with large ranges, such as *Umbra krameri*, these ranges have often been arbitrarily divided into small sections due to anthropogenic degradation of water systems. Since it is often no longer possible to restore the original condition, these sub-areas of an original large habitat are being stabilized at great expense as part of renaturation measures. A good example of this is the Fadenbach in the Donau-Auen National Park. Over 150 years ago, in the course of the major regulation of the Danube, many permanent and temporary water areas, such as the Fadenbach, were permanently separated from the main stream. Today, the Fadenbach represents one of only two habitats of *Umbra krameri* in Austria. In this habitat, which is severely threatened by succession, structural measures have been and continue to be carried out on a regular basis in order to preserve this isolated section of water as a habitat for *Umbra krameri* in the long term. In 2013, 50 *Umbra krameri* were removed from the Fadenbach and transferred to Schönbrunn Zoo for an ex-situ breeding program. Current genetic studies

of the Fadenbach population of *Umbra krameria* indicate that the wild population does not have a good long-term prognosis. It is also striking that the Fadenbach population and the ex-situ population originating from this watercourse differ significantly in terms of population genetics. This is surprising and concerning after such a short time. In order to sustainably manage populations with formerly large ranges, it is not enough to protect only the individual, isolated populations. Studies in which isolated populations from the same range are planned would be a good basis for the sustainable protection of *Umbra krameri*.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.